

THE INEVITABLE ROLE OF LITERATURE IN BUILDING INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION COMPETENCE AMONG EFL LEARNERS

Isheryakova Joanna Rinatovna

The second-year student of Bukhara State University, Foreign languages Faculty

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7880500>

Abstract. *This article focuses on the role of English literature in building intercultural and interlingual communication among EFL learners. Language and culture is connected with each other, and these two factors cannot be separated or exist in isolation. Language plays a vital role in culture. Language and culture are bound together and it takes its possession, when people begin interacting with each other. Utilizing language means utilizing culture of language's country. In countries where English is used as foreign language, people who begin to use this language in their daily conversation, they tend to use it as in their general interaction without focusing on its cultural differences. Hence, it is suggested to use literature texts in an effort to fascinate learners to Literature are rich source of sociolinguistic aspects. It includes a wide range of idioms, regional dialects, jargon, argon and etc. This material can be applied in four skills, reading, listening, writing and of course speaking. Furthermore, as it reveals daily life of nations in a certain culture, it develops the awareness about of a certain culture and tend to form their own characteristics as well. Hence, the article is going to discuss in what way teachers can build the intercultural communication competence among EFL learners.*

Keywords: *intercultural communication, EFL learners, intercultural communication competence, language, literature texts, pragmatics.*

INTRODUCTION

In today's global era, with improved technology, communication is necessary. Internet has contributed a lot producing a positive aspect in people's lives. When you study or work in a foreign land, you can easily come into contact by some social platforms and the language that is used in this intercultural communication is undoubtedly English

English lends a hand to EFL learners. Majority people can come in contact with different parts of the world, by using English language only. Besides, using and keeping an intercultural contact by English language. There are so many exchange programs, summer schools in which you can apply only by having an international certificate or without it in some cases, and this is of course a sign that indicates your knowledge and whether you are intercultural speaker or not.

Language and culture are connected with each other, and these two factors cannot be separated or exist in isolation. Language plays a vital role in culture. Language and culture are bound together and it takes its possession, when people begin interacting with each other. In school curriculum teachers should have different approaches in an effort to form an ability in using English for intercultural communication purposes. But, it is not always an easy task as you think, when it turns out in practice, not all teachers can deal with it and it is a time-intensive task

In essence, utilizing language means utilizing culture of language's country. In countries where English is used as foreign language, people who begin to use this language in their daily

conversation, they tend to use it as in their general interaction without focusing on its cultural differences.

Interlingual and intercultural communication. People need to communicate with each other, because communication is a sign of revealing human's existence on Earth and differentiating all human-being from animals. By communicating, people share feelings, emotions, reactions and come to know the personal traits and characteristics of people in psychological phase. Interlocutors come in contact with the localities and with foreigners, whose pronunciation is much various than from local ones, as well as each language has its own cultural aspects.

Each language is unique as it is formed in certain culture and it is definitely a powerful tool in interaction.

The learners of EFL should know by their teachers main components of communication, besides the regular rules, such as, grammar, pronunciation. There are four main components of communication:

1. *The goal of communication: to give, to obtain information*
2. *Consideration listener's motives, needs*
3. *Operating of communication: flexible, understandable*
4. *Effective performance: Organization and performance ideas*

While teaching, teachers should consider some factors that can really be handy for EFL students to take up a language with its culture. Teachers must teach learners a new foreign language by bounding language with its culture, in this way students can see the strong relationship between language and culture. Secondly, it is widely accepted to know the similarities and differences between culture and language. Teaching should not always focus on verbal communication, but the non-verbal communication cannot be avoided from attention at the same time. Teachers can develop these factors, firstly by knowing the aim of teaching, to enable learners to adjust their attitudes and develop their intercultural communication competence. To build intercultural communication competence is not enough only by providing theoretical skills from teachers, but there should be also enough practice in an effort to improve interlingual and intercultural communication competence.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

As some scientists have already mentioned a notion, that literature plays an enormous role in building a culture comprehension, it is still true phenomenon even nowadays. To build culture knowledge there should be created right strategies and authentic materials for EFL learners. As Bravo quoted by Aghagolzabeh and Tajabadi mentions that one of the main reasons why authentic materials are used in classrooms while teaching is due to the factor, that the learners will not encounter with an artificial language, but they can see a real world, language and how it is used. When the teachers use authentic materials in classrooms, learners will find them useful, as a tool of adaptation their psychology in different cultures. Literature as an authentic material converts a language in use and reveal written and verbal language by a certain cultural context. Texts can be taken not only from British literature, nowadays, there are so many experienced translators, who made a big contribution by translating many stories, novels from Russian, Uzbek, Turkish into English.

In addition, literature are rich source of sociolinguistic aspects. It includes a wide range of idioms, regional dialects, jargon, argon and etc. Literature texts are constructed in different genre and style. A character speaks variously according to the situation, this is called pragmatics, when

situation influence to the speech, and speech influences to the situation at the same time. So, it means that learners can use their speeches according to the situation, there may be situations when you should use formal spoken language, for instance, in the conferences, formal meetings and etc; and informal speech can only be used in the meetings, where it is not important to utilize formal speech. As Coliea and Starter quoted, by Rai state there are important four reasons why teachers are suggested to use Literature texts

1) *Valuable authentic material*, expose learners to face real life patterns
2) *Cultural Enrichment*, through novels and stories learners ability of comprehension can be developed in high degree, because they will see the process of communication, taking place in a certain culture

3) *Language Enrichment*, provided texts are full of naturalness which can introduce readers with colourful expressions, set patterns, discourse language

4) *Personal Involvement*, after reading the first passage of the story, learners can be fascinated by the feelings what will happen in the next passage of that story, how will end up a story with happy end or sad, they begin to show their emotional reactions, and this is of course can lead to personal Involvement

The goal of teaching English Literature is to build intercultural communication competence in order to facilitate learners to use this interaction by English language as a shared. Teachers should select literature texts according to the interests and motives of the learners, it is not necessary to use the whole text, but only a small part of the text, which learners can find interesting for themselves. The main factor that teachers should take into account while selecting texts is to consider the goal which will arise the interest of learners. The main point in teaching literature texts is that literature texts can develop the main four skills, such as reading, writing, listening and of course speaking. By skimming and skimming of the texts, learners can develop their reading comprehension skills. The following quotation is taken from novel Inspector, written by N.V. Gogol:

- Mayor. I have invited you, gentlemen, in order to inform you unpleasant news: an auditor is coming to visit us. Ammos Fedorovich. How is the auditor? Artemy Filippovich. How is the auditor? Mayor. An auditor from St. Petersburg, incognito. And with a secret prescription. Ammos Fedorovich. Here are those on! Artemy Filippovich. There was no concern, so give it up! Luka Lukic. Lord God! Even with a secret order! Mayor. I seemed to have a presentiment: today I dreamed all night some two extraordinary rats. Really, I've never seen anything like this. Black, unnatural size! Came, sniffed – and went away.

Firstly, in an effort to check a reading comprehension skill, students will be given some questions such as:

Who is an auditor and what is he doing?

Why were people surprised suddenly by hearing about his arrival? Is there any kind of reasons?

What does the dream mean? Why this dream was connected as a sign of the arrival of auditor?

Students can discuss these questions in pair work by collaborating their knowledge and ideas, in this task we can see a development of intercultural communication, because the text is originally written in Russian, not in English and students who are in pair also came with various cultures, where there are held different cultural patterns. Answers to the above-mentioned

questions will of course be various, so answers should be provided via small group presentation and each member of the group will talk and explain their ideas. This team-work can not only help with comprehension skills, but also build good critical thinking skills. The text can also will be used as for listening comprehension skill by watching a video or listening to the recorder.

Introduce new words such as: auditor, incognito, secret prescription, secret order, presentment, sniffed, unnatural size. In order, to rise the awareness of these words for students there can be done many interesting activities. For instance, teachers can provide some incomplete handouts in which students should complete empty places or students can just form sentences with these new words.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

By conducting the research among the students of 11-3GHTF-21 group of Bukhara State University it is revealed the cultural differences between students. As they were provided a part of text, they began to work in pairs, and exchanged with their valuable thoughts and ideas, in this way there was observed a development of critical thinking skills. Furthermore, they were not just focusing only on the text, but they have a good relationship with each other, which an important component of building intercultural communication competence. As, some students came from different cultural backgrounds, their way of thinking was different, but it is a good phenomenon, as students can not only communicate with each other, but also can be interested in one culture and know several information about a certain culture, for instance, their customs and values.

These findings can be an indispensable part in teaching system. Teachers can provide a small part of literature text and make students to think about that text, as well as facilitate a good relationship with each other and critical thinking skills

CONCLUSION

Literature is unique with its style and genre, as authentic material literature texts are the best method of teaching EFL learners to build intercultural communication competence and one of the main and interesting points of them is that, they can be applied in four skills: reading, writing, listening and speaking and besides these, it can develop knowledge of EFL students in critical thinking area as well. The literature texts should be selected according to the interests and motives of learners, if this will be in this case, learners can not only develop their interlingual and intercultural communication, but also can form their own characteristics by reading texts and observing a certain life of nations in the certain culture, this is definitely a crucial role of literature

REFERENCES

1. Aghagolzadeh, Ferdows and Tajabadi. Farzameh. A Debate on Literature as A Teaching Maaterial in FLT. In Journal of Language Teaching and Research Vol 3.no1 pp 205-210. January 2012. Academy Publisher Manufacture in Findland. 2012
2. Cruz.J.H.R. The Role of Literature and Culture in English Teaching Forum. 2010
3. Kecskes. Istvan. Intercultural Pragmatics.Oxford University Press. New York. 2014
4. Khatib,M.Rezaei,S and Derakshan, A. Literature in EFL/ESL classroom. ELT: 201-208. 2011
5. Rai, Asha. Use of Literature in Teaching English. In International Journal of educational Research and Technology. Vol 3. Pp. 71-80. 2012 September 2012. India
6. Stier. J. Internationalisation, intercultural Communication and Interculturar Competence in Journal of Intercultural Communication. Issues 11 2006